

A Deep Exploration of Poetic Expression: Critical Interactive Learning Through Technology and Ethics

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Abstract:

This study explores an innovative teaching approach that leverages technology to engage students in the profound world of classical poetry while fostering expressive abilities and ethical grounding. Recognizing the limitations of traditional rote learning methods that hinder creative thinking and communication skills, the research employs action research and student interviews to identify common challenges faced in poetry comprehension. The proposed model centers around multimedia instructional videos that elucidate the nuanced meanings and artistic conceptions inherent in classical poems. It guides students through a structured inquiry process, posing thoughtful questions that foster critical analysis, imagination, and the discovery of deeper symbolic interpretations. Beyond mastering literary techniques, the platform encourages peer collaboration, idea exchange, and constructive discourse, where students articulate perspectives, critique responses, and iteratively refine their understanding, sharpening communication skills alongside hermeneutic prowess. Crucially, the study emphasizes the ethical underpinnings of such a learner-centric pedagogy, advocating for responsible technology integration that respects student privacy while broadening access to diverse cultural viewpoints. The overarching goal is to nurture ethically-grounded lifelong learners capable of engaging with complex issues through open-minded reasoning and rhetorical artfulness. By seamlessly blending technological innovations with the timeless wisdom of classical poetry, this approach equips students with the expressive talents and moral discernment to navigate an increasingly interconnected world as empathetic, culturally-literate communicators and global citizens, addressing ethical concerns like privacy safeguards, digital rights management, and intellectual property protections to create a secure online environment for interactive learning while purposefully incorporating marginalized voices and counter-narratives to foster dialogues that transcend cultural boundaries.

Keywords: expression, expressive skills, poetry, ethic, teaching.

Introduction

In recent years, the possibilities for education have broadened significantly with the advance of technology, and this study considers the application of one such advance – cloud computing – and how it can help students understand and appreciate ancient Chinese poets.

Traditional classroom teaching has two components: students and teachers. Students absorb what the teacher teaches and answer questions accordingly. This kind of learning is one-way and students are passive receptors, seldom contributing their own ideas. As a result, they rarely learn independent, critical thinking skills. With traditional teaching, there may of course be exceptional teachers stressing the importance of independent thinking, but, generally, in a traditional classroom, active student participation is not the norm. Some teachers may apply student-centered teaching by encouraging students to think critically, but even in classes of moderate size, there are limits to how much time teachers have for individual instruction. For example, when the teacher asks a question, he or she may have several students eager to answer. When a student raises his or her hand, there is no guarantee that he or she will be asked either to supply the answer or that he/she will receive appropriate feedback. It is difficult, if not impossible, for every student in the class to have the opportunity to express themselves or to receive individualized instruction. For the students themselves, when they want to express and develop their own ideas, if the teacher fails to acknowledge their eagerness, the opportunity for effective learning is wasted. In this situation, without the teacher's immediate approval to answer the question, the student may lose interest. This inevitably leads to a diminishment of the teacher's lesson, since effective teaching is predicated on the assumption that the students' interest and attention are engaged. For this reason, many factors limit the effectiveness of traditional classroom teaching, including factors that cannot be controlled or foreseen. In view of this, this study attempts to devise a model of classroom teaching based on cloud computing, in the hope of helping teachers and students overcome the limits of traditional teaching. Its purpose is to allow students to think critically and independently, and to make good use of their creativity without the constraints of a traditional learning environment. In a cloud classroom students can speak without the teacher's intervention, learn voluntarily, understand according to their abilities, and enjoy the experience.

Before going further, it is important to note that there are four essential properties of classic poetry. Yu Yan (date of birth and death unknown), a critic in the late Song Dynasty (960-1279), proposed these properties which are described as follows:

- (1) *Direct expressions should be avoided.* Ideas and emotions should not be expressed directly through the literal meaning of the words; that is, word-choice should be tactful and uncertain, and direct expressions of key points avoided.
- (2) *Meanings should not be superficial.* There must be a deeper meaning behind the words.
- (3) *Context should not be obvious.* All characters and words are connected *between* the lines and these connections should not be apparent. Readers need to read carefully to find the context.
- (4) *Implications should not be brief.* The meaning behind the words should leave readers with an enriched understanding.

The above properties have one thing common: classic poetry has hidden implications for readers to consider. In other words, the poems' common feature is the implied meaning, which aims to allow readers, through his or her imagination, to find deeper meanings between the lines and to offer them the space to think and discover on their own. By this method, readers are left with an enriched understanding of the poet's intention and can further appreciate the artistry within the poetry.

Thus, the essential feature of classic poetry is that implications lead to deeper thoughts and

associations; that is, classic poetry does not require many words to transmit deep meanings and emotions. Such poems are like an iceberg: only a small part is visible; the most important part is hidden from view. The visible iceberg is a metaphor for the few words that classic poetry uses, and readers need to discover and explore the deep meanings hidden from view. To this end, this study integrates the new cloud technology with classic poetry to develop an innovative method to teach interpretation and criticism.

Classic poetry is fascinating because of its philosophic, social, linguistic, emotional and ethical implications (Chen, 2011). Traditional methods of teaching classic poetry often leave students isolated and bored, which is a pity because the poems are profound, moving and relevant. How, then, can we teach classic poetry in an interesting and lively way? (Wu, 2015). The key to successful teaching lies in the teaching method, which is as true for teaching classic poetry as it is for teaching music or science. By definition, an efficient teaching method can significantly improve student achievement (Ma, 2008), and so to teach classic poetry effectively means that students must learn to appreciate the artistic conception and integrity of the poems under study (Tsai, 2012). Once the teacher achieves this, his or her method of teaching can be considered effective (Chang, 2004); and if students learn to understand meaning and metaphor, surface and depth, exploring images constructed by them, their ability of appreciation and analysis will improve.

In fact, although learning classic poetry helps students improve their cultural literacy in a diversified way, the key issue for teaching it is how to interest them in the learning experience and how to structure it in an enjoyable way (Wang, 2012). Because there are many moods and emotions hidden in classic poetry, teachers must be able to identify them to make the lesson valuable (Ding, 2015). The open teaching method for classic poetry can improve not only linguistic abilities but also facilitate creativity and innovation in the interactions between teachers and students (Chen, 2005). Thus, based on the literature review above, cloud teaching is an innovative method for learning classic poetry – specifically, by helping them to think broadly and deeply about ideas and emotions that are shared by all of humanity.

Method

This study adopted the action research method, which is a qualitative research method often used to study teaching practices, with the purpose of exploring problems with student learning, analyzing them, together with the students' opinions, and designing an innovative teaching method to improve learning efficiencies (Tsai, 2013; Pan, 2007; Cheng, 2006; Lin, 2004; and National Taitung Teachers College, 2002). The research period of this study is from January 2011 to December 2015, a four-year period covering eight semesters. To identify the learning issues, the teaching consulting interviews with students were recorded and summarized. The steps are as follows: (1) apply a non-structural method so that students can ask questions about learning classic poetry; (2) outline the contents of student questions and clarify their key issues; (3) list indicators for the questions based on the key issues; and (4) summarize the question indicators. After identifying the problems, the research for an innovative teaching method was conducted. The concept for designing the new teaching method was cloud classroom teaching, using Yen Chou's "Border River Chant" as an example. The research focused on teaching practices, so the research limitation is that it was not possible to apply a qualitative method.

The design concept and process of the new teaching method are summarized thus: (1) transform the content in classical Chinese into smooth vernacular Chinese using two methods – adding more characters and finding removed terms; (2) transform descriptions of words into images to interpret the

author's situation; that is, to construct the environment described by the words; (3) transform the words into impressions so that every character represents an image and then to connect all images and create a general image of the situation; (4) go beyond, beneath and between the lines to find associations among them; (5) generate environmental elements based on the text, construct the atmosphere, and explore the symbolism based on the atmosphere; (6) organize all the constructed images based on the environments for the poetry and list all the features of each image; (7) for every scene described by the text, identify the sense used to perceive what was described, such as sight, sound, touch, and smell, and list the senses; (8) discuss the relationships between the symbolism and the author's moods; (9) discuss the symbolic meaning of scenery, sights, and living things in the images; (10) infer the implications of the characters and words; (11) list the questions regarding the appreciation of the poetry; that is, design questions for students to learn from and to think about the poem; (12) list student opinions for each of the questions on the bulletin board and the forum; and (13) design an open mechanism for students to construct an indicator for his or her ideas that was not covered by the indicators provided by the teacher, so that the student's creative thinking is not limited.

Results

The results of the research are in two parts. The first part summarizes those problems found with learning classic poetry, using the action research method. The second part concerns the new teaching method, which is designed to resolve the problems using digital cloud teaching and learning. The results are as follows:

A. Student problems with learning classic poetry

Student problems with learning classic poetry can be summarized as follows: (1) they could not thoroughly understand the meaning of the characters, words, and lines of the classic poetry written in classic Chinese; (2) they did not know how to think about the questions concerning one line of the poetry; (3) they did not know how to think about the context connecting two or more lines of the poetry; and (4) they did not know how to think about the meaning of the whole poem.

B. The design of the cloud teaching method for classic poetry

To resolve these issues, the cloud teaching method for teaching classic poetry was designed to: (1) provide interpretations and explanations for the characters, terms, and lines in classic poetry and to create teaching videos for students to watch, repeatedly if necessary, until they can understand the poems thoroughly; (2) design questions regarding one line of the poem for students to think about and answer, so that they can learn from each other's answers; (3) design questions regarding two or more associated lines for students to think about and answer, so that they can learn from each other's answers; (4) design questions regarding the whole poem for students to think about and answer, so that they can learn from each other's answers; (5) publish answers for reference, so that students can think again and express their opinions; and (6) announce learning indicators, so that students can think again and express their opinions.

C. Explanations and interpretations for the poetry

(A) Explanations for the characters

"Border River Chant", a 43-word poem. The meaning and Romanization of the characters are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The meaning and Romanization of the characters in “Border River Chant”

Line	Char.	Character in the original order						
		1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th
1	A	<i>Qiu</i>	<i>Yin</i>	<i>Shi</i>	<i>Qing</i>	<i>Jian</i>	<i>Xiang</i>	<i>Ming</i>
	B	Autumn	Haze	Sometimes	Clear up	Gradually	Return	Darkness
2	A	<i>Pien</i>	<i>Yi</i>	<i>Ting</i>	<i>Qi</i>	<i>Leng</i>	-	-
	B	Become	Whole	Yard	Desolate	Cold	-	-
3	A	<i>Chu</i>	<i>Ting</i>	<i>Han</i>	<i>Sheng</i>	-	-	-
	B	Long stand	Listening	Cold autumn	Sounds	-	-	-
4	A	<i>Yun</i>	<i>Shen</i>	<i>Wu</i>	<i>Yen</i>	<i>Ying</i>	-	-
	B	Clouds	Thick	No	Migratory bird	Shadow	-	-
5	A	<i>Geng</i>	<i>Shen</i>	<i>Ren</i>	<i>Qu</i>	<i>Ji</i>	<i>Jing</i>	-
	B	Night	Deep	People	Leave	Quiet	-	-
6	A	<i>Dan</i>	<i>Zhao</i>	<i>Bi</i>	<i>Gu</i>	<i>Deng</i>	<i>Xiang</i>	<i>Ying</i>
	B	Only	Shine on	Wall	Only one	Light	Mutual	Shine
7	A	<i>Jiou</i>	<i>Yi</i>	<i>Dou</i>	<i>Xing</i>	-	-	-
	B	Drunk	Already	All/both	Wake up	-	-	-
8	A	<i>Ru</i>	<i>He</i>	<i>Xiao</i>	<i>Ye</i>	<i>Yong</i>	-	-
	B	How	Can	Wear down	Night	Forever	-	-

(B) Interpretations of the poetry

“Border River Chant”, an eight-line poem. The interpretation from classical words into the vernacular for the poem is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. The lines from “Border River Chant” in vernacular Chinese

Line	The lines are translated from classical Chinese into vernacular Chinese based on their meaning
1	<i>The Autumn haze (shut down¹). Sometimes the sky cleared up and gradually returned to gloomy.</i>
2	<i>The whole yard became desolate and cold ².</i>
3	<i>I stood for a long time, listening to the sounds from the cold air.</i>
4	<i>The clouds were thick, and there was no shadow of any migratory bird.</i>

5	<i>It was late night and people were gone.</i>
6	<i>The land was completely silent.</i>
7	<i>There was only one lonely light shining on the wall, adding radiance to each other.</i>
8	<i>I had already sobered up. How, then, would I spend the endless night?</i>

Note 1: The words in parentheses were added to render the corresponding line's meaning complete.

Note 2: Inverted sentences.

D. Designing questions for each line

The questions designed for each line of "Border River Chant" are displayed in boxes, with one box for each question. These boxes have a number on top and an abbreviation character for the corresponding question. The questions were designed by the teacher. After the questions were published, the students could think about the questions and answer each one by clicking on the number on the box of that question. If they came up with a new question, they could add a new box for it. The cloud questions were designed as follows:

(A) Line 1

1. What does this line chiefly illustrate?
2. Was the skill of contrast applied to this line?

(B) Line 2

1. Was the skill of anastrophe (inverting the usual order of words or clauses) applied to this line?
2. Through which sense was the description perceived?

(C) Line 3

1. Where did the author stand for a long time?
2. Why did the author stand there?
3. What sound did the author hear?
4. How to interpret "Han Sheng"?

(D) Line 4

Based on the image, what is the implication the author tries to portray?

(E) Line 5

1. What is different about the description of time?
2. What is implied by the people leaving?
3. What is implied by the land being quiet?

(F) Line 6

1. What elements are described?
2. Which word is hidden?
3. What is involved in "Xiang Ying"?
4. What is the implication of this image?

(G) Line 7

1. Does the author wish to sober up?
2. What is the purpose of drinking?

(H) Line 8

1. Why does the author describe the night as lasting forever?
2. What is the author's mood?

E. Designing questions regarding two or more associated lines

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For two or more lines of “Border River Chant”, there is an ID on the left. Each question is displayed with a box. Each box has a number, with the question at the bottom. After the questions were published, the students could think about them and answer each question by clicking on the number on the box of that question. If they came up with a new question, they could add a new box for it. The cloud questions were designed as follows:

(A) Line 1 and Line 2

1. What do the descriptions of these two lines have in common?
2. What is the subject term?
3. Through which sense(s) is the description perceived?
4. What is the environmental atmosphere?
5. Are the words associated?
6. Is there any implication in the description of the environment?

(B) Line 3 and Line 4

1. Which direction does the author face?
2. Why does the author use the character “Ting”?

(C) Line 5 and Line 6

What is the context hidden within these lines?

(D) Line 7 and Line 8

What is the main implication of these two lines?

F. Designing questions regarding the whole poetry

The questions regarding the whole poem, such as questions about the subject, artistic conception, mood, and artistry, can be indicative of the overall context. The questions were numbered and listed. The students could use logic and reason to analyze the poetry and answer the questions. If they found an indicator not listed by the teacher, they could number and list on their own. The cloud questions were designed as follows:

(A) What is the subject of the poem?

(B) Is there any mood change?

(C) Is there any association between the environment and the feeling?

G. Publishing answers for reference

After the questions were designed, the deadline for answering had to be announced as well. All the answers were public and the students could discuss with each other. With the contents public, the students can see answers from different points of view and learn from them. After the deadline, the function of answering questions was removed. And the teacher published the answers.

(A) Answers published through the cloud system

a. Questions regarding one line

1. Line 1

(1) The big environment in autumn is shrouded in haze.

(2) “Yin (haze)” and “Qing (clear up)” contrast with each other. The temporary rays from the sun are used to set off the thickness of the haze.

2. Line 2

(1) “Pien (become)” is a verb. It was placed before “Yi Ting (whole yard)”, the subject term.

3. Line 3

(1) The yard

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(2) He is expecting some message from migratory birds.

(3) Cries of migratory birds

(4) “Han Sheng” is associated with “Qiu”. It can be interpreted as being in the cold autumn air.

4. Line 4

(1) There is not a single migratory bird found through his senses, which means that his hope for a letter brought by a migratory bird is dashed.

5. Line 5

(1) Implied by the night’s description, the time of the scenes described in the two previous lines is daytime.

(2) They are not the author’s family, otherwise they would have returned home with him.

(3) There is no one there, no voices at all.

6. Line 6

(1) A light and walls

(2) The author himself, the shadow

(3) The shadow and the light

(4) The author is alone without family.

7. Line 7

(1) No, it was not.

(2) He hopes that drinking can help him sleep and forget his worries.

8. Line 8

(1) Because of his sad mood, every second is a long time.

(2) He feels gloomy and his feeling cannot be described with words.

b. Questions regarding two or more lines

1. Line 1 and Line 2

(1) There are autumn scenes in the big environment and in the small yard.

(2) The subject term is autumn, as are all the words associated with autumn.

(3) The sense of sight through the eyes and the sense of touch in relation to the coldness

(4) It is an image of desolation.

(5) The character “Qiu” and the characters “Yin”, “Ming”, “Qi”, and “Leng” complement each other.

(6) The author expresses his feelings through the environment’s description.

2. Line 3 and Line 4

(1) The author looks up into the sky.

(2) Due to the thick haze and clouds, the author cannot see clearly, so he uses his hearing (Ting).

3. Line 5 and Line 6

(1) These two lines imply that there are people talking and laughing before it was late night.

4. Line 7 and Line 8

(1) The implication is that, with the depressed mood, the author feels that he could hardly live through the long, cold, autumn night.

c. Questions regarding the whole poetry

1. Line 1 implies that the author feels depressed. The depression deepens with each line. The final line shows the severest depression.

2. Through the description of the scenery in autumn, the author indirectly expresses his depression.

(B) The design for students to express their opinions regarding the answers through the cloud system

When the answers for reference were published, there was an “I want to express my opinion” button next to each answer. After clicking on the button next to an answer, two options would be displayed,

which are “agree” and “disagree”. The students could express their opinions regarding this answer provided by the teacher by selecting “agree” or “disagree”. For example, if 50 students expressed their opinions to this answer and 40 agreed with it, their opinions would appear on a page under Opinions of Agreement. The opinions of the 10 students who disagree would appear under Opinions of Disagreement. All the students could refer to these 50 opinions to think further about the questions from different perspectives.

H. *Announcing learning indicators*

After the teacher published the answers and discussed with the students, the learning ability indicators were then announced. The purpose of announcing the indicators in the final phase was to avoid the situation of the students being influenced by these indicators in terms of thinking, so that they could think independently. Showing the students the focus or positions of thinking after the students thought about these questions can aid critical thinking. The learning ability indicators for the questions designed for “Border River Chant” are as follows:

(A) The learning ability indicators announced through the cloud system

a. Questions regarding one line

1. Line 1

- (1) The ability to identify the meaning of the poem
- (2) The ability to identify the application of rhetorical skills

2. Line 2

- (1) The ability to identify the verb in the line
- (2) The ability to identify the description of feelings through senses

3. Line 3

- (1) The ability to identify location
- (2) The ability to identify the character’s image
- (3) The ability to identify the meaning of the special character
- (4) The ability to associate two characters

4. Line 4

- (1) The ability to identify the connection between character and scene and to discover the character’s mood

5. Line 5

- (1) The ability to identify whether the time of a scene is day or night
- (2) The ability to identify time and the implication of people leaving
- (3) The ability to identify the scene before the land became quiet.

6. Line 6

- (1) The ability to identify the description of items
- (2) The ability to identify the hidden elements in the description
- (3) The ability to identify the association between the items described and the phenomenon in the poem
- (4) The ability to identify the implication of the image presented by the poem

7. Line 7

- (1) The ability to interpret the author’s wish based on the text
- (2) The ability to interpret the purpose hidden in the text

b. The questions regarding two or more lines

1. Line 1 and Line 2

- (1) The ability to identify the differences and similarities between scenes

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- (2) The ability to identify key characters
- (3) The ability to identify the descriptions based on different senses
- (4) The ability to identify the meaning in emotions of the scene
- (5) The ability to identify the contextual relationship of a single character
- (6) The ability to identify the symbolic meaning of the description of a scene

2. Line 3 and Line 4

- (1) The ability to identify the association between the meanings of the lines
- (2) The ability to identify the special wording and to find the answer based on the implications between the lines

3. Line 1 and Line 2

- (1) The ability to identify the implication with two sides between the lines

4. Line 1 and Line 2

- (1) The ability to identify the image of the poem and to interpret the implication of the image

c. The questions regarding the whole poetry

1. The ability to identify the structure of mood transitions between or among the lines.
2. The ability to identify whether the poem describes a scene or portrays a character

(B) The design for students to express their opinions regarding the ability indicators through the cloud system

After the teacher published the ability indicators, there was an “I want to express my opinion” button next to each indicator. After clicking on the button next to an answer, two options would be displayed, which are “agree” and “disagree”. The students could express their opinions regarding this indicator provided by the teacher by selecting “agree” or “disagree”.

Suggestions

According to the analysis of this study, there are three aspects to the new learning model.

- (1) **Teacher-to-student.** Teachers must help their students to understand the new teaching method and encourage students to think creatively, so that both have a common reason to use creative learning.
- (2) **Student-to-student.** Individual brainstorming can then be advanced to general brainstorming among peer students and their sharing results. Through observations by and emulations among students, ideas can be deeper and broader.
- (3) **Student-to-teacher.** This involves the questions students ask their teachers and the learning ability indicators designed by the teachers. Students have an opportunity to express their thoughts fully.

The foundation of these three aspects lies in two new teaching measures. The first is that teachers must transform fundamental knowledge into media and / or teaching videos, to ensure that student learn effectively. The second is that after learning the fundamental knowledge, the students, with the teacher’s encouragement and guidance, think creatively and critically. The results may differ from student to student, but when they share their ideas with each other, the students gain a broader and deeper perspective of the ideas under consideration. Figure 1. shows the new cloud learning model based on these concepts.

“3I”: IT - Inspiring Thinking IR - Interactive Reference IF - Innovative Finding
 IBK: Instruction Basic Knowledge FSM: Finding Significant Matter

Fig. 1 “3 I” Cloud teaching model

The features of this model – deep understanding, thorough thinking, full expression, record sharing, discussion for clarification, modification after identification, and mutual observation and emulation – are similar to cloud learning. The purpose of building this teaching model is, hopefully, to apply it to other fields, as the indicators of this model are related to the digital age’s new learning concepts. Although this study designed the new cloud teaching method for classic poetry, its spirit reflects the key concept of all learning in the digital age.

Discussion

The traditional teaching method is to teach from the textbook. The teacher teaches the content of the textbook and his or her students learn by rote. Classic literature textbooks often contain several parts: (1) author, (2) explanatory note, (3) text, (4) annotations, (5) questions and discussions, and (6) extended reading. By this traditional method, teachers evaluate their students based on the content of the teacher’s lecture. Learning constraints may be generated and student thinking limited, restricting creative and critical teaching and learning.

Language skills are basic skills. Good language skills lead to good reading and comprehension, while weak language skills lead to poor reading and comprehension levels. One of the key indicators of effective learning is reading and comprehension literacy.

This study chose classic poetry from the field of language skills to design the cloud courses because classic poetry is written with concision. The poet’s words are carefully chosen to generate a poetic effect. Through the cloud teaching method, students are guided and encouraged to think for themselves. Since cloud technology has become a part of modern life, it must be applied to teaching or

we risk the latter's disconnection from the culture in which it occurs. Although we cannot prevent progress, we can govern it. Thus, teaching methods should keep pace with technology. With cloud technology, images, videos, and text can be integrated easily into any multimedia lesson, as this study using classic poetry shows. In a digital age, perhaps more so than in any other age, students need to learn how to think, to converse, and to comprehend – three skills the classical poets knew only too well.

There are five expansion discussion: 1. Limitations of Traditional Teaching Methods. The traditional teaching approach of lecturing from textbooks and rote learning is overly rigid. It lacks interaction and exploration, generating constraints that restrict the development of creative and critical thinking skills in students. An overdependence on passive knowledge transfer hinders their ability to think independently. 2. Language Skills as a Foundation. Strong language skills are the bedrock for good reading comprehension, while poor language abilities lead to low comprehension levels. Reading literacy is a key indicator of effective learning. Building solid language fundamentals should be prioritized. 3. Classical Literature Sparks Intellectual Curiosity. This study chose classical poetry to design cloud-based courses because of its concise yet poetic language. Poets carefully select words to create literary effects. The cloud teaching method guides students to think for themselves by engaging with these thought-provoking works. The depth of classical texts stimulates intellectual inquiry. 4. Modernizing Teaching with Technology. Cloud technology has become ingrained in modern living, so teaching methodologies must also evolve by integrating multimedia tools. This prevents education from becoming disconnected from cultural and technological advancements. While progress is inevitable, it should be governed appropriately. Pedagogy must keep pace through ethical tech adoption. 5. Fostering Holistic Competencies. In the digital age more than ever, students need to develop holistic abilities - independent thinking, expression, and interpretive understanding. The classical poets exemplified mastery of these very competencies. A well-rounded education should nurture these comprehensive skills.

The limitations of traditional rote learning methods highlight the importance of developing strong expression abilities in students. Passive knowledge transfer fails to equip them with the interpretive, expressive and critical thinking competencies needed to effectively articulate ideas and engage in substantive discourse. By guiding intellectual inquiry through the analysis of nuanced classical texts, cloud-based multimedia instruction can cultivate these vital expression skills. As the classical poets demonstrated mastery of concise, evocative language, studying their works provides a model for how to convey depth and complexity of thought with precision and rhetorical artfulness.

However, the modernization of teaching with new technologies also raises ethical considerations around the responsible adoption and governance of powerful tools like cloud computing and AI. While such innovations allow valuable multimedia integration and personalized learning pathways, they must be implemented thoughtfully. There are the following ethical concerns. The proper utilization of technology in education is a significant ethical consideration, particularly when it comes to incorporating technology into instructional methods. Ensuring student privacy and data security should be the primary focus when utilizing cloud computing and multimedia instructional films. Teachers and organizations must prioritize the usage of secure platforms and implement measures to safeguard student data from unwanted access or breaches. Furthermore, the utilization of technology must not result in a digital disparity, when pupils from socioeconomically disadvantaged families are put at a disadvantage due to insufficient access to essential gadgets or internet connectivity. Intellectual Property and Digital Rights Management: It is essential to uphold intellectual property rights when using multimedia resources and instructional videos. It is imperative for educators to guarantee that

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any digital work utilized or produced is appropriately licensed or acknowledged. This encompasses poems, photographs, and any supplementary multimedia resources. In addition to imparting ethical teaching techniques, it is crucial to educate students on the significance of protecting digital rights and intellectual property in the era of digital technology. Inclusivity and Representation: The curriculum ought to encompass a wide range of cultural perspectives and provide fair and accurate representation. Classical poetry frequently mirrors the prevailing cultural narratives of its era, potentially excluding or downplaying alternative perspectives. A morally principled approach to teaching classical poetry should encompass works from all cultural backgrounds and views, so guaranteeing that all students perceive their heritage and experiences mirrored in the literature they analyze. This encourages a broader and more diverse learning environment and enhances understanding and compassion for different cultures. The pedagogical approach should foster students' participation in ethical discourse and promote the development of critical thinking skills. Through the use of thought-provoking inquiries and the promotion of collaborative work among peers, students develop the ability to express their own viewpoints effectively and provide constructive feedback to others. This process facilitates the development of individuals' capacity to actively participate in intricate ethical dilemmas and improves their aptitude for moral thinking. Establishing a classroom atmosphere that values varied viewpoints and promotes ethical discourse is crucial. Striking a balance between tradition and innovation is crucial when using technology and contemporary teaching approaches. It is essential to harmonize these advancements with the timeless principles and sagacity found in classical poetry. Educators should strive to maintain the authenticity and profoundness of classical works while ensuring that they are easily understandable and captivating for modern students. This equilibrium guarantees that the intellectual and moral development, as well as the philosophical enlightenment, inherent in classical poetry, are preserved amongst the haste to modernize education. The ethical implications of hermeneutic analysis, which involves the interpretation of texts, necessitate the practice to be undertaken in an ethical manner. Students should be instructed to approach texts with intellectual humility, acknowledging the historical and cultural settings in which they were authored. This entails comprehending the constraints and predispositions of both the texts and one's own viewpoints. Ethical hermeneutics is recognizing these biases and endeavoring to achieve an equitable and impartial reading. The primary objective of incorporating ethics and expressive skills into classical poetry education is to cultivate individuals who are committed to lifelong learning with a strong ethical foundation. Students should possess the necessary abilities to navigate a world that is becoming more interconnected, demonstrating empathy, cultural literacy, and moral judgment. This requires not only acquiring proficiency in literary techniques but also cultivating the capacity to interact with ethical issues in a thinking and responsible manner. By acknowledging and resolving these ethical issues, educators can establish a learning atmosphere that upholds student rights, fosters inclusion, and cultivates the growth of critical and ethical thinking abilities.

Conclusion

Cultures change with technology, influencing all facets of society, including education. A key feature of modern education is adjustment and reform. Teachers must consider not whether they should adapt to new technologies but how they can keep pace with them and develop innovative teaching methods that integrate the best of science and culture. Contemporary education and modern teaching methods are very different than they were in the past, and indeed, it is inevitable that we apply technology to established teaching styles so that classroom instruction can be effective and

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relevant.

Classic poetry has deep philosophical roots that can be understood only by rigorous teaching. This study adopted the action research method to identify the problems that students often encounter while reading classic poetry. For this reason, the study designed a new learning method based on the problems using cloud technology, the principal concepts of which are summarized as follows: (1) to create teaching videos that are complete, concise, and easy to understand; (2) to design questions which can guide students to think critically and to train them to discover the meaning behind the words; (3) to design questions which guide students to contemplate meanings at ever-deeper levels and to train them to construct images from verbal descriptions of environments and atmosphere; (4) to design questions guiding students to make associative connections and to find implied or symbolic meanings in the poem; and (5) to discuss moods and related emotions extracted from the poem's context.

In these five key areas lies the essence of learning classic poetry, and this study explores their integration with cloud learning, giving students space for critical thinking so that learning classic poetry is neither dull nor boring but enjoyable and enriching. This is a question-based approach, nurturing the student's early appreciation of classic poetry and developing an understanding of ancient literature that is deep and profound. The goal of fostering holistic competencies like critical thinking relates to cultivating ethically-minded citizens who can engage with complex issues from multiple angles. Beyond technical proficiency, true mastery of expression demands developing skills like intellectual humility, moral reasoning, and the ability to build bridges across differences.

The rapid integration of technology into education necessitates careful consideration of ethical practices to ensure student privacy and data security are responsible uses of educational technology. Ensuring all students have equal access to educational resources is a fundamental ethical concern. The collection and use of student data require stringent ethical standards to protect personal information from misuse. Addressing and preventing cyberbullying and ensuring online safety are critical ethical responsibilities for educators and institutions. The shift to technology learning presents unique ethical challenges, including maintaining academic integrity and supporting students' mental health.

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